

USEFUL ASPECTS OF MEDICINAL PLANTS AND PLACES OF USE

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Annotation: *In this article, the description, classification, composition and useful aspects of medicinal plants that have been used in recent days and in the past have been clarified, and the places of use have been determined. During the writing of this article, comparison, calculation, experimental and historical methods were used and the intended goal was achieved.*

Key words: *Ether, curative, her, folk medicine, substance, pill.*

The history of the use of plants as medicine is equal to and closely connected with the history of mankind. In the early times, people used the plants growing around them to treat the sick. Conquest of lands, opening of trade routes, improvement of relations between peoples led to wide distribution and increase of types of medicines. Today, it is very common for people to prepare various forms of medicine from medicinal plants at home and use them. This certainly indicates that the population has sufficient medical knowledge and knowledge about medicinal plants. The synthesis of medicines by chemical means began much later. One of the main reasons for the further increase in the demand for medicinal plants and preparations obtained from them in the future in medicine is that the long-term continuous consumption of each chemical medicinal preparation obtained by synthesis leads to various unpleasant changes in the human and animal body. Accordingly, in recent times, the need for herbal medicines, phytopreparations and medicinal plants has been increasing all over the world. This, in turn, increases the importance of medicinal plants, leads to new scientific researches and the search for medicinal plants.

In some cases, the identification of medicinal plants cost a person dearly, because he first tested the effects of medicinal plants on himself. Zubtutum leaf healed a leg wound, and nettle leaf healed a burn. A piece of lemon fruit helps a hunter to hunt game without getting tired all day long, and a thousand devon fruit causes a person to shake his hands and feet and talk like a demented person.

In ancient times, due to the insufficient level of knowledge of people, plants seemed to them to be magical and fascinating. They believed that there are herbs that can find hidden treasures, take away unconsciousness, and make an unloved person fall in love. There are many legends about ginseng and oleander root, which look like

people. It was considered a miracle that ginseng root can give strength to people who are weak and exhausted. With the passage of time, science explained how certain plants can be used as a cure, and the legends disappeared by themselves. Some medicinal plants, for example, mint, are being propagated in plantations; Anyone who is resistant to brushing their teeth can enjoy peppermint oil daily.

People have been using medicinal herbs for the treatment of diseases since ancient times. 3-4 thousand years ago, India, China, Qad. In the countries of Egypt, works containing information about medicinal plants were written. In the East, especially in the folk medicine of Central Asia, treatment using medicinal plants has its own ancient traditions. Regarding the use of medicinal plants for medical purposes, Abu Ali Ibn Sina's work "Al-Qanun" contains information about the medicinal properties of about 476 plants and the methods of their use. Currently, the variety of medicinal plants has increased, and folk medicine is enriched with medicinal plants.

Medicinal plants are widely used for the treatment of humans and animals, prevention of diseases, as well as in the production of food, perfumes and cosmetics. There are about 12,000 species of medicinal plants on earth. Pharmacological and chemical properties of more than 1000 plant species have been investigated. There are more than 700 species of medicinal plants in Uzbekistan. Of these, about 120 species of plants grown in natural conditions and cultivated are used in the fields of scientific and folk medicine. Currently, almost 40-47% of medicines used in medicine are obtained from the composition of plants. Plants are living natural chemical laboratories with a complex structure, capable of creating complex organic substances and compounds from simple inorganic substances. Dried stems, buds, roots or rhizomes, nodules, bulbs, leaves, flowers, buds, fruits (seeds), juice, pulp or ether and other parts of medicinal plants are used as medicine.

Medicinal plants can be classified into 2 groups: 1) depending on the composition of active substances - alkaloids, glycosides, essential oils, vitamins, etc., 2) depending on their pharmacological levels - sedative, analgesic, hypnotic, cardiovascular system affecting, stimulating the central nervous system, lowering blood pressure, etc. The active substances of medicinal plants are alkaloids, various glycosides (anthraglycosides, glycosides affecting the heart, saponins, etc.), coumarins, flavonoids, astringent and mucilaginous substances, essential oils, vitamins, dyes, enzymes, may contain phytoncides, starch, proteins, polysaccharides, nitrogenous substances, fatty acids, oils and other compounds.

The effect of a medicinal plant on the body depends on the amount of chemical compounds in its composition. These compounds accumulate in various parts of the plant. The period of high effectiveness and quality of the drug corresponds to the time

of the beginning of their flowering and seeding period. Medicinal substances are collected in the bud, leaf or stem of some plants, in the flower or fruit of some plants, and in some in the root or bark. Therefore, the part of the plant with the most biologically active substances is harvested. Roots, rhizomes, bulbs and buds of plants are usually prepared during the period when the plant goes to sleep - in late autumn or before the awakening of the plant - in early spring. The fruits and seeds of the plant are harvested when they are ripe because they are rich in medicinal substances at this time. Freshly harvested medicinal plant products contain moisture (up to 85% in the above-ground organs, up to 45% in the roots). If this moisture is not removed (by drying), the plant will rot and the medicinal substances will break down and become useless.

More than medicinal plants, pomegranate, bittersweet, almond, dogwood, medicinal gulhary, walnut, jag-jag, zubturum, frankincense, dogwood, amonkara, pistachio tree, sachartki, chayot, shildirbosh, shirminiya, wormwood, yantoq, mint, kiikot, tograyhon, rubella, rubella, and others are widespread. Paxicarpine is obtained from bitter gourd, psoralen is used in the treatment of pes from aqquray, garmin is used in the treatment of fever, frankincense is obtained from anabazin, galantamine is obtained from a blackberry, spherophysin is obtained from a sedum and other alkaloids. An anthelmintic pelterin tanate and an extract are prepared from pomegranate seeds. Medicinal gulkhairi preparations are expectorants and softeners, medicines made from jag-jagi and lagochilus stop bleeding, and medicines made from pistachio and tea tree are used in the treatment of stomach diseases. S.Q. At the Islambekov Tashkent pharmaceutical plant, various topical medicines are prepared from medicinal plants grown and cultivated in Uzbekistan. The Institute of Chemistry of Plant Substances of Uzbekistan FA has a great service in finding medicinal plants and extracting alkaloids from them. In the institute, various organs of more than 4000 plants were studied in order to obtain alkaloids, and about 1000 natural compounds were isolated from them. On this basis, more than 20 valuable drugs such as cytisine and galantamine were created and introduced into medicine. The scientific staff of the Institute of Botany of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan and the laboratory of essential oil, medicinal and dyeing plants of the Botanical Garden, in cooperation with experts, prepared "Safro" made from the raw materials of medicinal plants, which are ecologically clean and highly effective in the treatment of jaundice (hepatitis), the most dangerous of the common infectious diseases in Central Asia. created the driver Hojimatov compound, and this compound was allowed to be used and produced in scientific medicine (1997). Also, the technology of planting medicinal plants is studied at the Department of Botany of SamSU, Tashkent State Institute of Pharmaceuticals. There are special farms

that grow medicinal plants in Tashkent, Namangan, Jizzakh, Samarkand, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya regions and Khorezm Mamun Academy.

Let's get acquainted with some medicinal plants below:

Mint is a rhizome perennial plant that grows in ditches. Leaves and stems are fragrant. Because this plant contains menthol and essential oils, which help calm the nerves. Mint leaves are eaten with liquid food or somsa. In the summer months, mint leaves are added to juice or compote to make a thirst-quenching drink. Mint clears phlegm, is widely used in the prevention of respiratory diseases, and in the treatment of liver diseases. A decoction made from its surface is recommended for the treatment of toothache and gum inflammation.

Namatak is a wild type of rose, mainly its fruit is used more. When a person's strength is reduced, in early spring, when the body lacks vitamins, a decoction of namatak is recommended. Namatak fruit increases a person's immunity. Vitamins are preserved more in a thermos-infused namataka than in a boiled one. The vitamin C contained in it thins the blood, lowers arterial pressure, and helps expel microbes from the body.

Frankincense is a perennial plant 30-60 cm tall. It grows in steppes and valleys. Medicinal properties of incense peak during the fruiting period of the plant. Its stem and seeds can be used as a sedative. Burning dried frankincense and smelling it a little will relieve headaches, and a decoction of its seeds will cure shortness of breath. When washing the face with a decoction of the plant, it helps to cure eye disease - cataract. Medicinal preparations of St. John's wort also have a hypnotic effect. Incense smoke, along with disinfecting houses, cleans the air in the room and prevents the spread of diseases.

Licorice is a rhizome perennial herb. In folk medicine, a decoction made from the rhizome is used as a cure for dry cough and sore throat. Licorice plant also has expectorant properties. In pharmacies, sweet licorice is sold in the form of syrup. It is especially recommended for young children when they have a cold.

Aloe is grown as a houseplant (Fig. 50). The leaves are dry and tender, after picking, they can be stored in a cool place for 10 days and then used as medicine. If aloe leaves are grated and eaten with honey, it is useful in the treatment of colds and gastrointestinal diseases. If medicinal plants are used properly, they will strengthen the body and cure various diseases in the body.

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